

FoTRRIS

Italian transition experiment

Examples of workshop output

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About the FoTRRIS project

FoTRRIS develops and introduces new governance practices to foster Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) policies and methods in Research and Innovation (R&I) systems. FoTRRIS stresses that RRI is a collaborative activity from the very beginning. Therefore, FoTRRIS adds the prefix 'co' to the acronym RRI. Important present-day challenges are of a global nature but manifest themselves in ways that are influenced by local conditions. Thus, FoTRRIS focusses on glocal challenges, i.e. local or regional manifestations of global challenges and on local opportunities for solving them.

FoTRRIS performs a transition experiment, i.e. an experiment to support the transformation of present-day research and innovation strategies into co-RRI-strategies. It designs, tests and validates the organisation, operation and funding of co-RRI competence cells. A competence cell is conceived as a small organisational unit, which functions as a local one-stop innovation platform that encourages various knowledge actors from science, policy, industry and civil society to co-design, -perform, and -monitor co-RRI-projects that are attuned to local manifestations of global sustainability challenges.

Since research and innovation systems and practices in EU member states and within different research performing organisations vary, FoTRRIS experiments the implementation of new governance practices in five member states. These five experiments are evaluated, validated and constitute the basis for FoTRRIS policy recommendations towards EU and member states policy makers so as to enforce co-RRI into the national and EU R&I systems. Training is dispensed to various stakeholders, so as to form them to establish other co-RRI competence cells. For more information see <http://www.fotrris-h2020.eu>

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Executive Summary

This document presents summary of the project activity – Transition Experiment - implemented in the frame of the WP: Test of the multi-actor experiment in the domain of resource scarcity. It described the main findings of the Transition Experiment, providing details about knowledge actors involvement in co-creation process.

Implementing Transition Experiment in Sicily

Transition experiment (TE) was implemented in the frame of the WP3: Test of the multi-actor experiment in the domain of resource scarcity. The main objective of the WP3 was to establish local/regional transition arenas in five participating partner countries (Austria, Belgium, Hungary, Italy, Spain) in order to develop co-RRI project concepts through a multi-actor exercise involving knowledge actors from research, civil society, policy, and the business sectors.

The guidelines for the implementation, facilitation and evaluation of the TE were prepared by the WP and WP Task Leaders and outputs are presented in the deliverables of the WP3 (D3.1 Report on co-RRI project concepts; D3.2 TEs Evaluation Report; D3.3 TEs Validation Report), which are available for the public on the FoTRRIS project website: <http://fotrris-h2020.eu/deliverables/>. As a methodological framework for the implementation of the transition experiments, the partnership used the MISC: Mapping Innovations on the Sustainability Curve - A methodological framework to accelerate the transition towards Commons Oriented Responsible R&I Systems (developed by Dr. Anne Snick): <http://fotrris-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/FOTRRIS-MISC-methodological-framework-CO-RRI.pdf>.

Figure 1. [FoTRRIS promotional video](#)

Workshop 1 – SYSTEMS MAPPING WORKSHOP

On 13 January 2017 the Sicilian FoTRRIS Competence Cell launched a series of workshops with local communities and policy makers of the Madonie region.

The first workshop was held at ARCA University Business Incubator in Palermo. The location itself represents a hub of innovation and entrepreneurship supporting research results transfer, scientific knowledge exploitation for the benefit of local communities, new business models and support to territorial development. The aim of the meeting was to map stakeholders' needs and obstacles for local development. The FoTRRIS MISC methodology was presented (see the presentation below) to the participants (i.e. local authorities at the municipal level, companies in the energy sector, researchers, representatives from the resident population). During the workshop some of the problems that affect the territory were highlighted:

- increasing depopulation process;
- competition with medium and large businesses able to supply the markets of large retailers;
- state of degradation of wide agricultural zones and reduction of the variety of traditional crops and local biodiversity products;
- land erosion and hydrogeological instability;
- external public capital and resources, industrial expertise and raw materials;
- fragmented educational offer in the school system, disconnected from the smart specialisation of the area and its productive excellence.

Contributions to the co-definition of the system goal in view of resilient energy communities in rural areas were also collected and the role of governance institutions and private actors highlighted. Lock-ins and leverages in the system were identified to analyse what prevents the institutions from steering effectively innovation processes and actors representing the niches from impacting on the whole system. At the end, participants tried to devise how they could pool their resources and skills to build an ecosystem of solutions to local challenges. After this workshop the Competence Cell members organised

The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) concept, as defined in the Madonie transition experiment in Sicily-Italy, called for a tight cooperation between societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations, etc.) during the research and innovation process, aims to introduce the values, needs and expectations of local society. Multi-actor participation and public engagement have been pursued as a key factor for positioning the project both in educational, business and civil communities, enabling the access to knowledge and to formal and informal learning processes.

The area of Madonie is in the centre of Northern Sicily, east of Palermo, and includes 21 urban centres, scattered in a mountain territory and characterised by a valuable natural heritage and landscape. Local sustainable development policies were driven by the local communities, focusing on people's quality of life and landscape management, recovering tradition and exploiting territorial assets, the connection between work and income of the producers, and the value of ecosystemic services for collective benefit.

The project was driven by the consciousness that a research and innovation system, in order to address the big territorial challenges, has to face a transition phase where comprehensive collaborative practices should be introduced.

The local Transition Arena (TA)* was set up to map the system and interesting experimental initiatives relevant to the theme of Sustainable Energy and to facilitate the interactions between research, innovation and local development actors and the representatives from the rural communities concerned (policy, business and citizens) by the energy transition process.

*Watch FoTRRIS video: <http://fotrris-h2020.eu/>

a reflection session (see the summary of the minutes below) and based on the results developed three themes, which could be analysed deeper and proposed for the discussions during the second workshop.

Summary of the minutes (in Italian):

- **Dal punto di vista della ricerca**, il percorso verso una ricerca responsabile è fondamentale, sia perché genera applicazioni tecnologiche sostenibili e responsabili, sia perché genera un approccio sistemico in cui il vantaggio apportato al sistema ricade sulle componenti del sistema stesso. La responsabilità è anche nel passaggio generazionale per sostenere il ritorno dei giovani nelle comunità interne e nei territori rurali. Il passaggio dalla ricerca ad una ricerca ed innovazione responsabile è spesso giocato sul piano politico; è invece importante trasferirlo sul piano operativo e l'energia è l'ambito ideale in cui alcune sperimentazioni possono essere condotte.
- **Dal punto di vista della governance**, non a caso la declinazione territoriale della SNAI è denominata "Madonie resilienti: laboratorio di futuro" e, nel campo dell'energia, vuole tendere all'obiettivo sfidante del 100% di produzione di energia da fonti rinnovabili, a cui dovranno e potranno concorrere cittadini, istituzioni, imprese e tecnici. Nel fare questo si recupera la memoria della tradizione e dell'identità culturale e si coniugano le politiche ordinarie per i servizi di cittadinanza con le politiche straordinarie della Commissione Europea per lo sviluppo locale. La novità di questa visione è quella di disaccoppiare la transizione energetica dalle scelte politiche, contrastando il blocco culturale, da un lato, e il blocco normativo e regolamentativo, dall'altro. In tal senso, l'attivazione di un circolo virtuoso sull'energia è speculare rispetto al ciclo del cibo, dei rifiuti ecc., nella visione sistemica della strategia. L'innovazione istituzionale (espressa ad esempio dal modello della città a rete) è fondamentale per avviare un sistema nuovo, interconnesso, di gestione dei servizi.
- **Dal punto di vista dell'economia e dell'industria**, si rileva che il 52% della produzione di energia sulle Madonie è da fonte rinnovabile, tuttavia questo dato non ha migliorato la condizione economica del territorio né il risparmio sulle bollette energetiche, perché riferito ad una economia di capitale, con concentrazione di grossi impianti. Quindi si deve puntare sulla generazione diffusa, sulla

individuazione di benefici per le famiglie e per i cittadini. Una delle principali innovazioni segnalate è quella della deconcentrazione degli investimenti verso le “fondazioni di partecipazione”, cui parteciperanno unioni dei comuni e cittadini tramite l’azionariato diffuso: più si contribuisce e si conferisce, più si ottiene in termini di risparmio energetico, con minori scarti e recupero di combustibile. Nelle fondazioni si può conferire sia valore monetario che servizi e patrimonio. Non vi sono azionisti di riferimento e si consente ad una comunità di recuperare vantaggi diffusi, perdendo un ruolo passivo di ricettore delle decisioni politiche per acquisire invece un ruolo attivo.

- **Dal punto di vista dei cittadini**, l’inversione culturale di rotta consiste nel sostituire l’esternalizzazione delle funzioni (es. amministratore/cittadino, produttore/consumatore) tipica dell’economia di capitale con l’internalizzazione (cittadini ‘prosumers’ di energia, presidi Slow Food), chiave di volta per attuare la curva della sostenibilità.
- **Dal punto di vista dell’istruzione e della formazione**, il valore generazionale deve essere focalizzato attraverso il ruolo delle scuole come asse portante della strategia, come già avviato all’interno della SNAI Madonie; la vision dell’energia si pone in perfetta sinergia con il piano dei laboratori nelle scuole finanziati dal MIUR e con la previsione di realizzare officine energetiche presso le scuole all’interno della SNAI.

Obiettivo del prossimo workshop, a Petralia Sottana (ex Mattatoio Comunale, via Duomo) , sarà quello di disegnare lo scenario futuro da raggiungere facendo leva sul potenziale identificato (governance, innovazione, resilienza delle comunità, efficienza, cooperazione, ecc..) e sulla rimozione delle barriere esistenti, procedendo ad un inventario delle soluzioni e attività innovative e alla scelta prioritaria degli interventi. Si propongono pertanto i seguenti tavoli di lavoro:

- Tema 1: Come raggiungere l’adesione di cittadini a comportamenti responsabili in ambito energetico (da una incentivazione economica ad una incentivazione relazionale).
- Tema 2: Come può la comunità in transizione diventare un Living Lab che, su base permanente e in modo sistemico, co-progetta il proprio sviluppo in modo responsabile e sostenibile.
- Tema 3: Come coniugare l’efficienza di prodotti e servizi ottenuta tramite l’innovazione con la ricaduta sociale in termini di miglioramento della qualità della vita.
- Tema 4: Governance partecipata e modelli di business per massimizzare le ricadute economiche locali della transizione energetica.

Project presentation for the invited knowledge actors:

FoTRRIS

Forecasting & Transition Studies, Responsible Research and Innovation, Consensus

Promuovere la transizione verso una ricerca e innovazione responsabile

www.cesise.org

Il periodo - 01/2015 - 01/2017

La Ricerca e l'Innovazione Responsabile:

- è un processo dinamico e iterativo;
- tutti i gruppi di interesse coinvolti nelle pratiche della ricerca e innovazione diventano mutualmente responsabili;
- questi gruppi condividono la responsabilità sia dei risultati sia del processo di ricerca e innovazione.

Il **RANKO** 2015: promuovere iniziative che, in un'ottica di Ricerca e Innovazione Responsabile, prevedano la realizzazione di attività di dialogo con la società civile.

Lo scopo & L'obiettivo

- FoTRRIS ha lo **scopo** di favorire la transizione dal sistema di ricerca e innovazione (R&I) attuale ad un sistema di ricerca e innovazione responsabile (RRI).
- L'**obiettivo** di FoTRRIS è di offrire metodi efficienti ed efficaci ai ricercatori, ai cittadini, alle imprese e ai responsabili dei processi decisionali politici per risolvere le sfide 'globali' utilizzando il metodo co-RRi.

Fasi di implementazione

Co-RRi

- La nostra metodologia fa affidamento sulla progettazione di **arene di transizione** associate a un'unità di supporto chiamata **cellula di competenza**.

Le arene di transizione

- Le **arene di transizione** sono gruppi di persone interessate alla co-risoluzione della sfida globale.
- La **cellula di competenza** includerà ricercatori qualificati nelle metodologie co-RRi che condivideranno le loro conoscenze con i membri dell'arena di transizione.

- il progetto FoTRRIS si occuperà di **sviluppare ulteriormente il concetto di co-RRi, una metodologia stage-gate per garantire una risposta standardizzata e responsabile alle sfide globali**, insieme al concetto di arene di transizione e di cellula di competenza.
- Sarà programmata una **piattaforma di collaborazione online** per permettere ai membri delle arene transizionali di lavorare insieme, seguendo la metodologia stage-gate.

- Verranno eseguiti **esperimenti di transizione in 5 paesi** (Austria, Belgio, Ungheria, Italia e Spagna) per testare e convalidare le idee di FoTRRIS e gli strumenti collaborativi.
- In seguito, il Consorzio si occuperà di diffondere i risultati il più possibile, e di garantire la piena di questi risultati a livello politico. Inoltre, miriamo a fornire delle **linee guida politiche per incoraggiare lo sviluppo delle arene di transizione con l'aiuto delle istituzioni pubbliche**.

Oggi?

Sperimentazione della transizione

Cosa facciamo?

MISC - Mappatura delle Innovazioni sulla curva di Sostenibilità

Scopo della metodologia non è sviluppare conoscenze scientifiche o teorica, ma per facilitare (cooperazione di diversi soggetti) la transizione e lo sviluppo di soluzioni creative per i complessi problemi di oggi

MISC - transizione sociale

- Tutti gruppi di interesse deve essere presentati
- Essere d'accordo -Nostro scopo
- Attori principali e regimi, pionieri
- I cambiamenti del sistema economico e monetario
- Problemi quale non possiamo risolvere
- Il nostro progetto

Workshop 2 – VISIONING

The second workshop was held on 3 March 2017 at EXMA, a local meeting space, in Petralia Sottana in the Madonie region.

The workshop objective was to design a future scenario to be achieved using as leverage the potential identified (in terms of governance, innovation, community resilience, efficient use of resources, cooperation) and removing existing barriers, and to proceed to an inventory of solutions and innovative activities and to the identification of priority interventions to be launched.

25 stakeholders participated in the workshop and the discussions about what should be done to bring change, making use of potential leverages and overcoming constraints, took place in three groups of about 5/7 people. Groups' work was facilitated by three moderators.

- Group 1 co-created ideas to address: How to achieve the citizens' engagement towards responsible behaviour in the energy field (from economic incentives to relational benefits) and to co-design sustainable and responsible local development, on an ongoing basis and in a systemic view?

Goal: Work plan for an awareness action and internalisation of functions to be carried out on a territorial basis – Submission of a Living Lab proposal within the 11th Wave ENOLL membership April 2017.

Note: This goal was selected as central one for the third workshop, as knowledge actors agreed on the aim to foster Living Lab impact on the territory.

- Group 2 co-created ideas to address: How to match effectiveness of innovation products and services with the social spill-over effects in terms of quality of life improvement?

Goal: Scale-up of niche innovation on broader territorial impact, new ideas for RRI projects relevant to the area.

- Group 3 co-created ideas to address: Participatory governance and business models to maximise the local effects of energy transition.

Goal: Identify the most appropriate business models for citizens' shareholding (participatory foundation, short networks and local supply chains, ESCO, social enterprises, sharing/circular economy).

All groups were involved in an active co-creation process using techniques such as round table, debates, group work and brainstorming. The last stage of the workshop was to present the ideas to all participants during the final panel session. As the goal of the TE according to FoTTRIS should be a project proposal, and based on the needs of the local community and governance, participants agreed that the topic of Group 1 was the most relevant and could be realised in a project idea in a shorter timeframe.

Workshop 3 – PROJECT CONCEPT DESIGN WORKSHOP

Based on the results of the second workshop and reflection meeting of the Competence Cell members who were developing Madonie Living Lab project concept, the third workshop was organised in the Madonie area. It introduced the project concept to a restricted audience* consisting of about 12 people including researchers, SOSVIMA (local governance) development agents and representatives from companies, policymakers and citizens. The co-design of the steps to be taken, the timeline, the resources needed, the risk analysis and management and the communication initiatives were presented.

The Madonie Living Lab structure was discussed, in particular:

- its distinctive features;
- its multi-stakeholder partnership;
- its organisation, management and governance;
- communication and open innovation for user engagement;
- appropriate facilities and infrastructure;
- expertise which is needed to be gathered;
- the sustainability of its business model;

- critical success factors and risks.

The project, developed by the FoTTRIS competence cell, invited participants to workshops and SOSVIMA as the local development agency, capitalised on the results of other EU-funded projects and initiatives (STS-Med, ZERO-PLUS, HABITATS). It used the Living Lab approach to support the MaLL – Madonie Living Lab concept as an overall methodological framework to facilitate the participatory planning process, involve different groups of stakeholders – citizens, administrators and local companies – in the co-creation and joint development of platforms and services connected to glocal challenges and in the establishment of a smart & green community.

MaLL was also meant to be a territorial innovation hub in which all actors of the Inner Areas Strategy would participate, a network of physical and virtual spaces for the development of suitable solutions for glocal challenges, and a link between the pillars of the sustainable rural development strategy for Madonie area through demonstration and scale-up actions.

The MaLL project aims to: a) support local communities through participation in experimenting new approaches to responsible research, innovation and entrepreneurship; b) provide equipped spaces and facilities to allow competence and experience sharing; c) match the demand of local communities for strategic planning of sustainable development, quality of life improvement and smart management of local resources.

International acknowledgement within the ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs has been asked for to learn new methodologies for the growth of rural communities through the participation in integrated projects, to exchange good practice through contacts with international organisations and associations, to search for mobility opportunities for students, staff and professionals.

The implementation process of the MaLL project includes four main steps:

- Vision at the political and administrative level and participation to maximise local value creation, raising awareness and community empowerment.
- Knowledge and design thinking (analysis of data, promotion of idea-generation initiatives).
- Demonstration of appropriate technologies in relevant, open environments.
- Business models (attracting investors and partners, project financing and crowdfunding, cross-sector engagement, co-ownership).

RRI will inspire the innovation process design in MaLL to link the innovation topics to effective local needs, to foster open consultation of stakeholders, to promote user-driven idea-generation supported by an open innovation platform, to set up dedicated innovation labs to accelerate solution development and validation by final users.

Note: The third workshop was restricted to the facilitators of the process (innovators, local development agents and researchers, supervised by local authorities) to formulate the roadmap of the Living Lab project (MaLL).

Conclusions

For more detailed information about the TE, please contact Sicilian Competence Cell: <http://fotrris-h2020.eu/italian-competence-cell/> .